

A Tale of Two Viruses: Seroepidemiological and a Cross-Sectional Insights into HIV/HBV Coinfection in Selected Hospitals in Rivers State, Nigeria

Elenwo Mercy¹, Oketah Edith Nnenna², Okerentugba Phillip O.³, Okonko Iheanyi O.⁴

^{1,2,3,4} Virus & Genomics Research Unit, Department of Microbiology, University of Port Harcourt, Choba, Port Harcourt, Rivers State, 500102 Nigeria.

⁴ORCID ID: 0000-0002-3053-253X

ABSTRACT

Published Online: October 12, 2023

Background: Hepatitis B virus (HBV), a circular DNA virus with humans serving as the only reservoir, remains a worldwide public health problem. The similarity in transmission routes for HBV and HIV makes co-infection very common. Thus, this study aimed at unveiling the seroepidemiological patterns of HBV coinfections among HIV-infected individuals in some selected hospitals in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Materials and methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted on 350 HIV-infected individuals attending ART clinics at selected hospitals in Rivers State, Nigeria. Sociodemographic data were collected based on interviewer-based questionnaires, and clinical history was obtained from participants' medical records. Serological analysis for HBsAg was done using the ELISA method.

Results: Of the 350 HIV-infected patients, 9(2.6%) were positive for HBsAg. The majority of HIV/HBV coinfecting participants were in age groups ≥ 41 (3.7%), females (2.9%), singles (3.0%), tertiary education holders (3.5%), and business owners (1.1%). Furthermore, immunological and virological markers analysis revealed that HBV seropositivity is more common with patients having a CD4 count of 350-499 cells/mm³ (6.2%) and viral loads as a target not detected (TND) with 5.4%.

Conclusion: This study observed an HIV/HBV coinfection rate of 2.6% which has further confirmed the persistence of HIV/HBV co-infection in Rivers State, Nigeria. Ongoing and persistent public health interventions among the study population are thereby advocated.

KEYWORDS:

Antibodies, Coinfection, HCV, HIV, Rivers State, Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

One of the frequent complications in HIV-infected patients is dual infection with HBV and coinfection with hepatitis B is common among HIV-infected individuals (Okonko et al., 2022). Hepatitis B and HIV infections are significant public health problems in sub-Saharan Africa, and research suggests that co-infected individuals with either HBV or HIV experience a higher rate of HIV progression (Ugwu et al., 2023a). HBV and HIV infections are major global health problems in Sub-Saharan Africa (Im et al., 2022; Okonko &

Shaibu, 2023), with over 2% of the population infected with HIV and at least 8% infected with hepatitis B (Matthews et al., 2014; Ihongbe et al., 2022).

HBV infection is a significant global public health issue (Cookey et al., 2022; Okonko et al., 2023a). Globally, it is estimated that 5%–10% of people living with HIV are co-infected with hepatitis B virus (HBV), while HIV/HBV frequency in sub-Saharan Africa varied from 0.0% to 28.4% (Stabinski et al., 2015; Cyrille et al., 2019; Adesegun et al., 2020; Oti et al., 2021; Ihongbe et al., 2022). The global prevalence of hepatitis B virus (HBV) infection among people infected with human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) is 7.4%, according to the World Health Organization (2019), and about 1% of people infected with HBV (2.7 million people) are also infected with HIV (Rai et al., 2007; Ihongbe et al., 2022). A fifth of the current global population is

Corresponding Author: Okonko Iheanyi O.

**Cite this Article: Elenwo Mercy, Oketah Edith Nnenna, Okerentugba Phillip O., Okonko Iheanyi O. (2023). A Tale of Two Viruses: Seroepidemiological and a Cross-Sectional Insights into HIV/HBV Coinfection in Selected Hospitals in Rivers State, Nigeria. International Journal of Clinical Science and Medical Research, 3(10), 185-190*

Elenwo Mercy et al, A Tale of Two Viruses: Seroepidemiological and a Cross-Sectional Insights into HIV/HBV Coinfection in Selected Hospitals in Rivers State, Nigeria

estimated to be seropositive for HBsAg (Sharma et al., 2005; Akindigh et al., 2019).

Nigeria has one of the highest chronic viral hepatitis disease burdens in the world (Cookey et al., 2022; Okonko et al., 2023a). The prevalence of HIV/HBV co-infection in Nigeria is reported to range between 10% and 70 % (Omatola et al., 2019; Ugwu et al., 2023b). As of 2013, an estimated 13.6% of the Nigerian population had been reported to be chronic carriers of HBsAg (Musa et al., 2015; Akindigh et al., 2019). Consequently, the burden of disease is considered to be high, as evidenced by the high incidence of morbidity and mortality associated with the virus (Lok, 2005; Akindigh et al., 2019).

Co-infection with HIV and HBV viruses causes complex interactions (Ihongbe et al., 2022). Coinfection of HBV with HIV is associated with significant morbidity and mortality globally (Okonko et al., 2023b). HBV infection poses hazards to antiretroviral therapy (ART)-related liver damage, limits CD4 recovery, accelerates immunologic progression, and increases morbidity and mortality in HIV-infected patients (Wandeler et al., 2013; Ihongbe et al., 2022). Although co-infection with HBV has been linked to higher HIV RNA turnover, increased liver morbidity, and complex HIV pathology, it is not typically considered in the therapy of HIV infection (Wandeler et al., 2013; Ihongbe et al., 2022). Thus, this study aimed at unveiling the seroepidemiological patterns of HBV coinfections among HIV-infected individuals in some selected hospitals in Rivers State, Nigeria.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

The study was carried out in selected areas of Rivers State in Nigeria, in an urban setting with a population of 7,034,973.

Study population

The study population included male and female individuals living with HIV that attend ART clinics at the Rivers State University Teaching Hospital, Military Hospital and Modern Primary Health Care Center, Rumuji. Three hundred and fifty (350) HIV-infected individuals were selected and participated in the study. Individuals included in the study were males and females confirmed and documented as being positive for HIV infection that are on ART. While individuals who decline and HIV negatives were not included in the study. A random sampling irrespective of age, gender and ethnicity was done to ensure that sampling was representative of Rivers State, Nigeria. Socio-demographic data such as age, sex, marital status, education and occupation and clinical data for every participant were obtained using a questionnaire.

Sample Collection and Preparation

Blood samples (about 5ml) were aseptically collected from the participants during routine investigations, after obtaining written informed consent from the participants. The samples were collected into sterile EDTA bottles and plasma samples were obtained after centrifugation. Samples were appropriately labelled and stored in two aliquots at -20°C and -80°C until analysis.

Serological Analysis of Hepatitis B Surface Antigen (HBsAg)

Serum samples were analyzed for HBsAg using the ELISA kit (DIA.PRO Diagnostic Bioprobes, Italy). The tests were performed according to the manufacturer's instructions.

Data analysis

Data were systematically analyzed as appropriate. The chi-Square test was done using SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) software.

RESULTS

Table 1 shows the HIV/HBV coinfection rates relating to their sociodemographic characteristics, immunological and virological markers. Of the 350 HIV-infected patients, 9(2.6%) were positive for HBsAg. The majority of HIV/HBV coinfecting participants were in age groups ≥ 41 (3.7%), females (2.9%), singles (3.0%), tertiary education holders (3.5%), and business owners (1.1%) as shown in Table 1. Furthermore, immunological and virological markers analysis revealed that HBV seropositivity is more common with patients having a CD4 count of 350-499 cells/mm³ (6.2%) and viral loads as a target not detected (TND) with 5.4% as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: HIV/HBV Coinfection relating to their sociodemographic characteristics, immunological and virological markers

Variables	Number tested	HBV +ve	%HBV +ve	Chi-square test
Age (years)				
≤ 20	35	0	0.0	
21 -40	206	5	2.4	
≥ 41	109	4	3.7	
Sex				
Males	147	3	2.0	
Females	203	6	2.9	
Marital Status				
Married	227	3	2.0	
singles	123	6	3.0	

Elenwo Mercy et al, A Tale of Two Viruses: Seroepidemiological and a Cross-Sectional Insights into HIV/HBV Coinfection in Selected Hospitals in Rivers State, Nigeria

Educational Status			
Primary	54	0	0.0
Secondary	190	6	3.2
Tertiary	86	3	3.5
None	20	0	0.0
Occupations			
Student	48	2	0.6
Business owner	191	4	1.1
Working class	145	3	0.9
CD4 (Cells/mm³)			
<200-349	162	3	1.9
350-499	65	4	6.2
>500 above	123	2	1.6
Viral load (Copies/ml)			
TND	111	6	5.4
<40	79	1	1.3
40-1000	73	1	1.4
>1000	92	1	1.1
TOTAL	350	9	2.6

DISCUSSION

This study aimed at unveiling the seroepidemiological patterns of HBV coinfections among HIV-infected individuals in some selected hospitals in Rivers State, Nigeria. We observed a serological prevalence of 2.6% among these HIV-infected individuals. This observed result is much lower than the 14.0% reported from Rivers State, Nigeria in 2022 (Okonko et al., 2022) and 6.6% from another of our studies earlier on in Rivers State, Nigeria (Okonko et al., 2023b). The reported value here is much lower than the 17.7% reported from Awka, Anambra State, Nigeria (Ugwu et al., 2023a) and 40.9% in Onitsha, Anambra State, Nigeria (Ugwu et al., 2023b). Our observed 2.6% is also lower than the 14.7% reported in Gombe State, Nigeria (Precious et al., 2022), 10.87% reported in Japan (Demarchi et al., 2022), 10.5% in Ethiopia (Gedefie et al., 2023), the 9.2% in Jos, Plateau State, Nigeria (Akindigh et al., 2019), the 9.20% in Gambia (Bittaye et al., 2019), the 8.8% in Addis Ababa (Seyoum et al., 2022), the 8.6% in Ethiopia (Goa et al., 2019), the 7.8% in Southeast, Nigeria (Nnakenyi et al., 2020), the 7.6% in Southeast Nigeria (Odita et al., 2023), the 6.7% in Port Harcourt, Nigeria (Okonko et al., 2015), the 6.3% in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria (Innocent-Adiele et al., 2021), the 6.1% in Tanzania (Nyalika, 2021), the 6.0% in the northern Nigerian communities (Adesegun et al., 2020), the 5.5% in Keffi, Central Nigeria (Oti et al., 2021), the 4.83% in Douala, Cameroon (Cyrille et al., 2019), the 4.0% in Banik et al.

(2022), the 3.62% in Nepal (Bhattarai et al., 2018), the 3.6% in Ogun State (Ihongbe et al., 2022), the 3.5% in Anyigba, Kogi State, Nigeria (Omatola et al., 2019).

This 2.6% prevalence of HBV reported here is much lower than the WHO's threshold for high-endemic areas (WHO, 2010; Okonko et al., 2022). Nigeria is ranked as one of the countries that are hyper-endemic for HBV infection (> 8%) (Ajuwon et al., 2021; WHO, 2021; Okonko et al., 2022). However, the 2.6% we reported here is comparable to the findings of other similar studies in Nigeria and overseas. It tallies with the global prevalence of HIV/HBV co-infection, which varies from 1.13% to 59.0% (Lawal et al., 2020; Ugwu et al., 2023b). The 2.6% reported here is similar to the 2.0% reported from Yenagoa, Bayelsa State, Nigeria (Okonko & Shaibu, 2023), the 2.0% and 2.1% in Port Harcourt, respectively (Okonko et al., 2020; Aaron et al., 2021), the 2.1% in Lagos, Nigeria (Odukoya et al., 2022), the 3.1% reported previously in Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria (Cookey et al., 2021) and the 2.5% from Ibadan, Nigeria (Okonko et al., 2012). It is higher than the 1.0% reported in our previous study from Warri, Delta State, Nigeria (Okonko et al., 2023a). These reports which show differences in regional prevalence may point to different epidemiological factors at work in different parts of the country and reveal a gap in our current understanding of the epidemiology of HIV/HBV co-infection. Moreover, this is probably the reason why there are variations in HIV prevalence and the frequency of HIV co-infection with HBV/HCV (Oluremi et al., 2021; Tassachew et al., 2022). National surveillance systems to provide a full picture of the co-infection landscape are urgently needed to identify epidemiological trends over time to make sure suitable prevention measures are deployed (Akindigh et al., 2019).

Among these HIV/HBV co-infected patients, the prevalence was higher among age groups ≥ 41 . This observation supports that of Bhattarai et al. (2018), Akindigh et al. (2019), Cyrille et al. (2019), Gedefie et al. (2023), Okonko and Shaibu (2023) and Okonko et al. (2022, 2023b), who also reported a higher prevalence within the age group 41 and above. However, the observation in this study deviated from that of another previous study in Nigeria and overseas (Adesegun et al., 2020; Mutisya et al., 2021; Oti et al., 2021; Ihongbe et al., 2022; Cookey et al., 2022; Odita et al., 2023; Okonko et al., 2023a; Ugwu et al., 2023a, b), where a higher prevalence occurred among age group ≤ 41 years.

Among these HIV/HBV coinfecting participants, the prevalence of HIV/HBV co-infection was also higher among the females (2.9%) than their male counterparts (2.0%), which corresponds with other previous studies in Nigeria (Adesegun et al., 2020; Nnakenyi et al., 2020; Cookey et al., 2022; Okonko et al., 2022; Precious et al., 2022; Gedefie et

Elenwo Mercy et al, A Tale of Two Viruses: Seroepidemiological and a Cross-Sectional Insights into HIV/HBV Coinfection in Selected Hospitals in Rivers State, Nigeria

al., 2023; Okonko & Shaibu, 2023; Okonko et al., 2023a, b, Ugwu et al., 2023a) where a higher prevalence was reported among females than males. However, this observation also contradicted the work by Bhattarai et al. (2018) and Ugwu et al. (2023b), where the co-infection was higher in males.

In terms of marital status, HIV/HBV coinfecting singles had the highest prevalence. This observation contradicted previous studies in Nigeria and abroad (Adesegun et al., 2020; Oti et al., 2021; Okonko et al., 2022, 2023a; Okonko & Shaibu, 2023; Ugwu et al., 2023a) who reported the highest prevalence in the married participants and some among the separated/divorced or widowed. However, the findings of this study on marital status-specific coinfection correspond with other previous reports in Nigeria and overseas (Bhattarai et al., 2018; Cookey et al., 2022; Ihongbe et al., 2022; Okonko et al., 2023b; Ugwu et al., 2023b).

HIV/HBV coinfection in relation to their educational profiles indicated that those with tertiary education backgrounds were more in proportion. This finding contrasted other similar studies (Bhattarai et al., 2018; Adesegun et al., 2020; Oti et al., 2021; Okonko et al., 2022; Ugwu et al., 2023a,b) reported in Nigeria. However, this observation supports other previous studies (Ihongbe et al., 2022; Okonko & Shaibu, 2023) in Nigeria.

HIV/HBV coinfection in relation to their occupational categories indicated that business owners constituted a higher HIV/HBV coinfection rate (1.1%), closely followed by the working class (0.9%) compared to students (0.6%). This observation corresponds to Okonko et al. (2022) in a previous study in Port Harcourt, Nigeria where self-employed dominated. This observation, however, deviates from the findings of other similar and previous studies (Adesegun et al., 2020; Oti et al., 2021; Okonko & Shaibu, 2023; Okonko et al., 2023a; Ugwu et al., 2023a, b), where higher coinfection rates were reported mostly in students, civil servants in some cases, among others.

Additionally, in terms of CD4 status, a higher HIV/HBV coinfection rate was observed in patients with a CD4 count of 350-499 cells/mm³. Similar observations were made in previous studies in Nigeria and overseas (Opaleye et al., 2014). Although, other studies reported higher rates in patients with <200 cells/mm³ (Ojide et al., 2015; Boateng et al., 2019; Nnakenyi et al., 2020; Okonko et al., 2020; Innocent-Adiele et al., 2021; Okonko & Shaibu, 2023; Ugwu et al., 2023a), 200-350 cells/μl (Ugwu et al., 2023b) while Okonko et al. (2023b) reported higher coinfection rates among participants with CD4 counts 500 & above. This finding may not correspond with the proposition that coinfection deteriorates the immune status leading to poorer

outcomes (Nnakenyi et al., 2020). This study may also observe a reverse from the claims that individuals with a CD4 cell count of less than 200 cells/mm³ have a 16.2 times higher risk of liver-related deaths than those with a CD4 count of greater than 350 cells/mm³ (Falade-Nwulia et al., 2012; Boateng et al., 2019; Nnakenyi et al., 2020).

Furthermore, the viral loads of the HIV/HBV coinfecting participants did not follow any definite patterns. A higher co-infection rate occurred among coinfecting patients with targets not detected (5.4%) which was followed by those with 40-1000 copies/ml (1.4%). This finding is comparable to that of other studies (Okonko et al., 2023b; Ugwu et al., 2023a). However, this assertion is at variance with some studies in Nigeria (Okonko et al., 2020; Innocent-Adiele et al., 2021; Precious et al., 2022; Okonko & Shaibu, 2023; Ugwu et al., 2023b).

CONCLUSION

This study observed an HIV/HBV coinfection rate of 2.6% which has further confirmed the persistence of HIV/HBV co-infection in Rivers State, Nigeria. Ongoing and persistent public health interventions among the study population are thereby advocated.

Conflict of interest

None declared.

REFERENCES

1. Adesegun, O. A., Olaniran, O. H., Bamidele, E., Inyang, J. N., Adegbe, M., Binuyo, T. O., Ehioghae, O., Adeyemi, O., Oyebisi, O., Idowu, A. O., & Ajose, O. (2020). HIV-hepatitis co-infection in a rural community in Northern Nigeria. *The Pan African Medical Journal*, 36, 352. <https://doi.org/10.11604/pamj.2020.36.352.23978>
2. Akindigh TM, Joseph AO, Robert CO, Okojokwu OJ, Okechalu JN, Anejo-Okopi JA. Seroprevalence of hepatitis B virus co-infection among HIV-1-positive patients in North-Central Nigeria: The urgent need for surveillance. *Afr J Lab Med*. 2019;8(1), a622. <https://doi.org/10.4102/ajlm.v8i1.622>
3. Bhattarai M, Baniya JB, Aryal N, Shrestha B, Rauniyar R, Adhikari A, Koirala P, Oli PK, Pandit RD, Stein DA, & Gupta BP. (2018). Epidemiological Profile and Risk Factors for Acquiring HBV and/or HCV in HIV-Infected Population Groups in Nepal. *Hindawi BioMed Research International* Volume 2018, Article ID 9241679, 7 pages. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2018/9241679>
4. Cookey, T. I., Odenigbo, K. C., Okonko, B. J. & Okonko, I. O. (2022). Prevalence of HBsAg among

Elenwo Mercy et al, A Tale of Two Viruses: Seroepidemiological and a Cross-Sectional Insights into HIV/HBV Coinfection in Selected Hospitals in Rivers State, Nigeria

- patients attending a tertiary hospital in Port Harcourt, Nigeria. *International Journal of Life Science Research Archive*, 03(02), 125–134
5. Cyrille NDO, Jaccotting Thierry E N, Symphorien E, Clemence O, Dieudonné A. Hepatitis B and C, HIV, Syphilis Seroprevalences and Asymptomatic Carriage of Hemoparasites Among Blood Donors at the Douala General Hospital in Cameroon, Central Africa. *Biomed J Sci & Tech Res* 18(5)-2019. BJSTR. MS.ID.003227.
 6. Falade-Nwulia O, Seaberg EC, Rinaldo CR, Badri S, Witt M, Thio CL. Comparative risk of liver-related mortality from chronic hepatitis B versus chronic hepatitis C virus infection. *Clin Infect Dis*. 2012; 55:507-513
 7. Gedefie A, Seid A, Fenta GM, Tilahun M, Shibabaw A & Ali A. (2023). Hepatitis B and C virus infections and associated factors among HIV-positive and HIV-negative tuberculosis patients in public health facilities, Northeast Ethiopia: A comparative cross-sectional study. *SAGE Open Medicine* 11: 1–12
 8. Ihongbe J. C., Enitan S.S., Dada M. O., Ofem O. G., Effiong E. J., Kemiki O. A., Ogbonna A. F. (2022). Detection of Hepatitis B Virus Serological markers among Adult HIV Positive Female Patients on HAART in Ogun State, Nigeria. *Qeios* ID: YLB5K9, pp:1-25. <https://doi.org/10.32388/YLB5K9>
 9. Lawal, M. A., Adeniyi, O. F., Akintan, P. E., Salako, A. O., Omotosho, O. S., & Temiye, E. O. (2020). Prevalence of and risk factors for hepatitis B and C viral co-infections in HIV-infected children in Lagos, Nigeria. *PloS one*, 15(12), e0243656. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0243656>
 10. Lok A. Hepatitis B virus infection and liver transplantation. *J Virol*. 2005;24: 112–114.
 11. Matthews PC, Geretti AM, Goulder PJ, Klenerman P. Epidemiology and impact of HIV coinfection with hepatitis B and hepatitis C viruses in Sub-Saharan Africa. *Journal of clinical virology*, 2014; 61(1): 20-33.
 12. Musa BM, Bussell S, Borodo MM, Samaila AA, Femi OL. Prevalence of hepatitis B virus infection in Nigeria, 2000–2013: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Niger J Clin Pract*. 2015;18(2):163–172. <https://doi.org/10.4103/1119-3077.151035>
 13. Nnakenyi, I. D., Uchechukwu, C., & Nto-Ezimah, U. (2020). Prevalence of hepatitis B and C virus co-infection in HIV positive patients attending a health institution in southeast Nigeria. *African health sciences*, 20(2), 579–586. <https://doi.org/10.4314/ahs.v20i2.5>
 14. Ojide CK, Kalu EI, Ogbaini-Emevon E, Nwadike VU. Co-infections of hepatitis B and C with human immunodeficiency virus among adult patients attending human immunodeficiency virus outpatients clinic in BeninCity, Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Clinical Practice*, 2015; 18:516-521
 15. Okonko, I. & Shaibu, N. (2023). HIV/HBV Coinfections Among People Living With HIV/AIDS in Yenagoa, Bayelsa, Nigeria. *Qeios*, CC-BY 4.0, p.1-21. Article, March 7, 2023, [doi:10.32388/VWRIG1](https://doi.org/10.32388/VWRIG1).
 16. Okonko, I. O., Asagba, O. H., Okonko, B. J. & Baeka, G. B. (2023a). Prevalence of Hepatitis B Virus Coinfection Amongst HIV-Infected Patients in Capitol Hill Hospital, Warri, Delta State, Nigeria. *Cancer Biology*, 13(1):1-12
 17. Okonko, I.O., Adewuyi, S.A., Omatsone, C. & Cooney, T.I. (2020). Detection of Hepatitis B Virus Among HIV Positive Fresh Undergraduate Students in Port Harcourt, Nigeria. *Asian Journal of Research and Reports in Gastroenterology*, 3(3): 8-13
 18. Okonko, I.O., Biragbara, M. T., Cooney, T. I., Okonko, B. J., Adim, C. C. & Innocent-Adiele, H. C. (2023b). Serological Evidence of HBV, HCV and HEV Infection Among ART-Naïve HIV-1 Infected Individuals in a Tertiary Health Facility in Port Harcourt, Nigeria, from 2016 – 2017. *American Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Development (AJMRD)*, 5(04):48-57
 19. Okonko, I.O., Okobia, V. C., Cooney, T. I., & Innocent-Adiele, H. C. (2022). Dual Positivity of Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV) and Hepatitis B Virus (HBV) In the Highly Infected Population of Rivers State, Nigeria. *Report & Opinion*, 14(10):1-9
 20. Opaleye OO, Oluremi AS, Ogbolu DO, Babalola BA, Shittu T, Adesiyana AA. Prevalence of hepatitis-B virus infection among HIV patients in Ikole Ekiti, South-Western, Nigeria. *Asian Pac. J. Health Sci.*, 2014; 1(4): 507-511.
 21. Oti VB, Mohammed IH, Ibrahim Y, Ibrahim C, Orok I, et al. (2021) Epidemiologic Survey of HBV, HCV and HIV Infections in a Pregnant Women Population in Central Nigeria: A Cross-Sectional Study. *J Infect Dis Epidemiol* 7:194. doi.org/10.23937/2474-3658/1510194
 22. Precious DN, B Olumide O, Temitope ST, Seth AT, Dawa BA, Yanan BT, et al. (2022). Hepatitis B and C Co-Infection among HIV-Positive Patients Attending ART at General Hospital Kaltungo, Gombe State, Nigeria. *J Immuno Allerg*. 2022; 3(2):1-7. DOI: [https://doi.org/10.37191/Mapsci-2582-6549-3\(2\)-038](https://doi.org/10.37191/Mapsci-2582-6549-3(2)-038)

Elenwo Mercy et al, A Tale of Two Viruses: Seroepidemiological and a Cross-Sectional Insights into HIV/HBV Coinfection in Selected Hospitals in Rivers State, Nigeria

23. Rai RR, Mathur A, Mathur D, Udawat HP, Nepalia S, Nijhawan S. Prevalence of occult hepatitis B & C in HIV patients infected through sexual transmission. *Tropical Gastroenterological Journal*, 2007; 28(1): 19–23.
24. Sharma SKJ, Saini N, Chwla Y. Hepatitis B. Virus: Inactive. *Curr Immunol J*. 2005;2:82.
25. Stabinski L, O'Connor S, Barnhart M, Kahn RJ, Hamm TE. Prevalence of HIV and hepatitis B virus co-infection in sub-Saharan Africa and the potential impact and program feasibility of hepatitis B surface antigen screening in resource-limited settings. *JAIDS Journal of Acquired Immune Deficiency Syndromes*, 2015; 68: S274-S285.
26. Ugwu, C. H., Oketah, E. N., Okerentugba, P. O., Frank-Peterside, N., & Okonko, I. O. (2023a). Co-infection of Hepatitis B among HIV-infected patients: A cross-sectional study from A University Teaching hospital in Anambra State, Nigeria. *Journal of Clinical Case Reports Medical Images and Health Sciences (JCRMHS)*, 4(3):1-6
27. Ugwu, C. H., Oketah, E. N., Okerentugba, P. O., Frank-Peterside, N., & Okonko, I. O. (2023b). Serological Evidence of HIV/HBV Co-infection among HIV-infected patients in Onitsha, Anambra State, Nigeria. *GSC Biological and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 23(03):001-008
28. Wandeler G, Gsponer T, Bihl F, Bernasconi E, Cavassini M, Kovari H, Yerly S. Hepatitis B virus infection is associated with impaired immunological recovery during antiretroviral therapy in the Swiss HIV cohort study. *The Journal of infectious diseases*, 2013; 208(9): 1454-1458.
29. World Health Organization (WHO) (2019). Hepatitis B vaccines: WHO position paper, July 2017. Recommendations. *Vaccine*, 37(2): 223-225.